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The Effects of Stimulus Pre-Exposure and Conditioning on Overt Visual Attention

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Three experiments (a, b, c) combined to provide a well-powered examination of the effects of stimulus pre-exposure and conditioning on visual attention using an eye tracker and a space-shooter video game where a colored flashing light predicted an attacking spaceship. In each, group “control” received no pre-exposure to the light, group “same” received pre-exposure in the same context as conditioning, and group “different” received pre-exposure in a different context. Experiments differed in visual details regarding the game (1a vs. 1b and 1c) or minor details in the setup of the eye tracker (1a and 1b vs. 1c). Overall, pre-exposure retarded acquisition of keyboard responding. That effect was enhanced, rather than attenuated, by a context change. Separating participants by sign and goal trackers showed the context change enhanced the pre-exposure effect in goal trackers and reduced it in sign trackers. Visual attention to the light declined during pre-exposure and did not recover with either conditioning or a context switch. Visual attention to the light decreased during conditioning. Visual goal tracking toward where the spaceship would appear was also retarded with pre-exposure. Unlike the keyboard responding, a context change led to more normal goal-tracking acquisition. Results are discussed in terms of theories of attention and the potential effects of demand characteristics on the task.

Keywords: latent inhibition, sign tracking, goal tracking, eye tracking, visual attention

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The present study presents an empirical contribution to the literature on conditioned-stimulus (CS) pre-exposure effects by monitoring overt visual attention to the events during pre-exposure and conditioning and providing a preliminary assessment of differences between sign- and goal-tracking individuals. It is widely known that exposing a CS prior to conditioning generally retards the rate at which conditioned responding is acquired, and the procedure is commonly referred to as “latent inhibition.” The present article provides eye-tracking data as a measure of changes in overt visual attention devoted to the CS during what is, ostensibly, a latent-inhibition procedure where changes in attention and attention-related variables are thought to operate.

As summarized elsewhere (see Nelson et al., 2021), the specialist will recognize that the retardation observed after pre-exposure could result from conditioned/differential inhibition or “learned irrelevance” accruing to the CS in cases where the outcome is also expected or occurring (e.g., Bonardi & Hall, 1996; Miller et al., 1991). The retardation could also be due to pre-exposure habituating or extinguishing the “alpha” response to the CS (Kimble, 1961, p. 55; Lubow et al., 1968) when that response is similar to the conditioned response (Lubow et al., 1968; Nelson et al., 2021). When the possibilities above are ruled out, the retardation observed might be accepted as a case of the latent-inhibition phenomenon (e.g., Lubow & Moore, 1959; Nelson et al., 2021).

We used the same video-game method and procedures as were used in the experiments presented in Nelson et al. (2021). Participants were trained to respond to the appearance of enemy spaceships. Then, in a conditioning phase, a flashing light predicted the occurrence of one of the spaceships. Over trials, participants came to emit the spaceship-associated response in the presence of the light. Groups that had received pre-exposure to the light showed less of that learned response than did those who did not. Moreover, the effect of pre-exposure was context specific, as is the case with latent inhibition (e.g., Byron Nelson &

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del Carmen Sanjuan, 2006; Hall & Channell, 1985). Responding was less attenuated when pre-exposure and conditioning took place in different contexts. Summation tests (e.g., Reiss & Wagner, 1972; Rescorla, 1969) showed that the light did not function as a conditioned inhibitor. The blocked sequence of pre-exposure and conditioning ruled out a learned-irrelevance account (see also Bonardi & Hall, 1996). The degree to which habituation of alpha responding to the light could occur did not impact the effect of pre-exposure. Empirically, the effect Nelson et al. demonstrated was consistent with the latent-inhibition phenomenon, and their data were consistent with the theoretical account of latent inhibition offered by Wagner (1981; see Nelson et al., 2021, for discussion).

Wagner's (1981) theorizing, and other models that incorporate a similar mechanism, predict that latent inhibition results from CSs being predicted by contexts or other stimuli present in the situation (e.g., McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000). Another class of models assumes the result is related to attention and related factors, such as associability and salience (e.g., Hall & Rodríguez, 2010; Haselgrove et al., 2010; Le Pelley, 2004; Lubow et al., 1981; Mackintosh, 1975; Pearce & Hall, 1980; Pearce & Mackintosh, 2010). Though the attentional theories disagree as to the reasons, they all predict that attention/associability to the CS should decline during pre-exposure.

A number of experiments have used eye tracking to look at differences in the allocation of overt visual attention, and the relationship between gaze position and visual attention has been documented and discussed elsewhere (e.g., Deubel & Schneider, 1996; Kruschke et al., 2005; Posner, 1980). With respect to conditioning procedures, the research has generally examined the within-subject allocation of attention between stimuli that vary in their predictiveness (e.g., Beesley & Le Pelley, 2011; Kruschke et al., 2005; Le Pelley et al., 2011; Wills et al., 2007). Results commonly show that more predictive stimuli command more attention than less predictive stimuli. Presently, we can find no such independent assessment of visual attention as it relates to simple preexposure and conditioning in humans.

In rats, attention to stimuli appears to decrease during pre-exposure and then recover, at least initially, during conditioning. For example, Kaye and Pearce (1987; see also Kaye & Pearce, 1984) habituated rats' orienting to a light over 12 sessions and then paired the light with the delivery of milk over four sessions in a conditioning phase. Throughout conditioning, contact with the milk dipper in the presence of the light, a type of goal-tracking response, was greater in the nonpre-exposed group than in those that had been pre-exposed to the light. That is, latent inhibition was demonstrated. During pre-exposure, orienting to

the light clearly decreased over sessions. During conditioning, orienting to the light in the pre-exposed group was less than in the nonpreexposed group in the early sessions of conditioning. The orienting response to the light did recover during conditioning in the preexposed group and did not differ from that of the nonpre-exposed group at the end of the short training schedule. Thus, latent inhibition of goal tracking was observed, along with evidence of reduced attention to the CS during pre-exposure and early in conditioning.

Experiments in the series reported here measured the allocation of overt visual attention with an eye tracker to assess the effects of pre-exposure and conditioning on that attention in humans. The experiments used the space-based video-game method and procedures used by Nelson et al. (2021; see also Nelson et al., 2014). The game instructs participants how to respond on a keyboard to repel particular spaceships when they appear, and each response is further conditioned to its respective ship with practice trials. In this way, the spaceship can produce a response for use in subsequent conditioning (e.g., Ivanov-Smolensky, 1927). Then, the game transports participants to a galaxy (i.e., context) containing an animated space station that participants have to protect from invaders (e.g., of the apparatus; see Figure 1). Colored sensors

Figure 1

Apparatus Used in Experiment 1a With the Sensor (Red Light) Embedded in a Control Panel (Top) and in Experiments 1b and 1c With the Control Panel Absent (Bottom)

Note. Top and bottom panels show the different background contexts used. Circular and rectangular outlines on the bottom panel illustrate the areas of interest. The circle surrounding the sensor is the sensor area. The rectangular areas near the center of the screen are the near zones, and those at the left and right edges are the far zones. The right side represents the outcome zone, and the left side is the other zone. See the online article for the color version of this figure.

appear that can predict the appearance of invading spaceships (see the red light in both panels of Figure 1). As these sensors become associated with the spaceships that they predict, participants come to emit the keyboard response attached to each ship prior to their arrival. Nothing is required of the participant during intertrial intervals (cf., Byron Nelson & del Carmen Sanjuan, 2006). Participants simply sit at the computer and experience the contextual elements of the game.

The design of the experiments (see Table 1) was simple and involved three groups. Following the phase where responses were attached to the spaceships, groups “same” and “different” received six pre-exposures to a flashing-light stimulus (a “sensor” in the game). During this time, group “control” was simply exposed to the context. Next, uninterrupted, all groups received 10 trials where the flashing light was paired with an attacking spaceship. In group different, the pairings occurred in a different space-background context than where pre-exposure took place. These contexts were counterbalanced, and all groups received equal exposure to both contexts during pre-exposure. It was expected that participants would begin to respond to the sensor prior to the

Table 1
Design of Experiments

Group	Pre-exposure	Conditioning
Control	A: — / B: —	
Same	A: 6R- / B:—	A: 10R+
Different	A: — / B: 6R-	

Note. A: and B: are different space-background contexts where gameplay takes place. Contexts were equally exposed during pre-exposure, and both their identity and order in the trial sequences were counterbalanced. R- indicates pre-exposure to a flashing red sensor light. R+ indicates pairings of the light with an attacking spaceship to which the participants have been previously trained to respond. — indicates exposure to the background context. Group same received pre-exposure and conditioning in the same contexts. Group different received pre-exposure and conditioning in different contexts. Group control received no pre-exposure to R.

¹ Nelson et al. (2021) used sensors that were either red (as in the present experiment) or green, and these were factorially combined with spaceships that were either red (as in the present experiment) or green. Only one quarter of the participants in that experiment used

arrival of the spaceship as the two events were associated. That responding was expected to emerge more slowly in group same than in groups control and different (see Nelson et al., 2021).

In addition to the keyboard responding, we recorded where on the screen participants were looking during the trials. We expected visual attention (orienting) to the sensor to decline during pre-exposure. In conditioning, the orienting should still be low during the first few trials of conditioning and then recover (e.g., Kaye & Pearce, 1987) before perhaps declining again (e.g., Kaye & Pearce, 1984). Additionally, Nelson et al. (2019) demonstrated that eye tracking can be used to measure conditioned responding in the form of goal tracking (see also Schad et al., 2020). As participants come to expect the occurrence of a spaceship in the presence of the sensor signal, they direct visual attention to the area of the screen where the spaceship will arrive in anticipation of its arrival. Gazing in this task is an unrestricted behavior and occurs naturally to the appearance of the stimuli; it requires no pretraining to occur in the situation. Evidence suggests that, to a large extent, gaze behavior is an unconscious, involuntary process (see Hopkins et al., 2015, 2016; Madipakkam et al., 2016). With these unconditioned-response characteristics, the direction of gaze toward areas where stimuli are expected to appear, in the presence of predictive cues, may represent a “purer” form of elicited conditioned responding than the keyboard behavior that has to be trained to be evoked by the spaceship outcome.

To foreshadow the results, and clarify the presentation of the experiments, Experiment 1a showed a robust effect of pre-exposure in the keyboard responding, but there was no effect of the context change where our previous work (Nelson et al., 2021), using the same method and parameters,¹ showed that the effect of pre-exposure was attenuated with a context switch. The resulting pattern in the data was for there to be more effect of pre-exposure with a context change than without it. One variation from the experiment presented in Nelson et al. was that, here, the sensor was embedded in a “control” panel in Experiment 1A (Figure 1, top panel) where it appeared alone in Nelson et al. As that panel was present in both contexts, it could serve to attenuate the effect of a context change based on mechanisms proposed by Wagner (1981; McLaren & Mackintosh, 2000) whereby contextual elements are associated with the stimuli, reducing their ability to be conditioned. Experiment 1b replicated Experiment 1a exactly but had the sensor panel

the exact same stimuli as used here. However, analyzing the pre-exposed groups in that experiment with the CS color variable showed no effect of the color of the CS and no interaction with group, $p_s \geq .236$.

removed, as in Nelson et al. (2021; see Figure 1, bottom panel). Again, the effect of a context change was, if anything, to increase the effect of pre-exposure. Experiment 1c was an exact replication of Experiment 1b with a minor modification to the eye-tracking apparatus setup. It, again, produced the same results where there was numerically a stronger effect of pre-exposure with a context change. As the experiments are practically identical, we will present them as one experiment with three replications, including “experiment” in the analyses.

We also performed exploratory analyses of the data with the participants broken down by whether they were predominately sign trackers, preferring to look at the signal predicting the upcoming spaceship, or goal trackers, preferring to look for the appearance of the predicted ship, at the end of training. Those analyses suggest interesting differences in what individuals may have learned during pre-exposure. How that learning might interact with context is brought out in the “Discussion” section.

Method

Participants

Participants were university students who were paid €5 for their participation. They were predominately college aged and approximately 65% female. In each experiment, we planned for 16 participants per group but recruited more appointments than necessary to compensate for no shows. No participant who showed for their appointment was turned away. The turnout was good. Referring to groups control, same, and different, respectively, random assignment placed 22, 23, and 25 participants in those groups in Experiment 1a; 24, 26, and 29 in those groups in Experiment 1b; and 21, 22, and 21 in those groups in Experiment 1c. Participants provided written consent, and all procedures were approved by the Commission of Ethics for Research and Teaching of the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU; M10/2015/210).

Apparatus

The apparatus is the same as that used by Nelson et al. (2019, 2021) and is adapted here with permission from Nelson et al. (2019). The apparatus was a three-dimensional first-person video game presented in detail in Nelson et al. (2014), and relevant visual details not described below are illustrated there. The game was played on one Dell OptiPlex computer with a 22-in. screen with an aspect ratio of 1.6 (width/height). The resolution was set at 1,280 x 800 pixels.

Below the screen, a SensoMotorics Instruments RED 250 eye tracker was placed to monitor the participants’ gaze, which works with the participants natural pose and freely moving head (i.e., no chinrest). The monitor and eye tracker were surrounded by a white 1-m cube box, with the front side removed in Experiments

1a and 1b. In Experiment 1c, the white box was replaced with a trapezoidal box constructed of black foam board with rectangular ends and the front face uncovered. The opening was 70 cm by 70 cm, and the back wall was 70 cm by 50 cm (width x height); the overall length of the side walls was 1 m. The front opening allowed participants to sit at the table with their head and shoulders just inside the box. This box replicated the box used by Nelson et al. (2021), though no eye tracker was used there.

Participants were seated approximately 60 cm from the monitor, though that distance was modified on a per-participant basis as required for the eye tracker to acquire their eyes. The researcher was positioned behind a desk and two computer monitors at the immediate right of the participant, with the distance between the participant and the researcher being approximately 1 m.

Participants’ view on the screen was as if they were inside of a spaceship looking out of a view screen. The view screen contained a crescent-shaped control panel near the bottom that contained two rows of oval, canister-shaped devices (Figure 1, top panel). There were five on the first upper row and three on the lower row. Each of these could be illuminated with any color, and red (RGB 255,0,0) was used in all experiments. The illumination consisted of a 20-s on/off flashing of color at a rate of three cycles per second. The diameter of each canister was 50 pixels when lit. The third canister from the left on the top row was used to present red. In Experiments 1b and 1c, the control panel was removed (Figure 1, bottom), and the canister-shaped sensor device was absent until illuminated; then, it appeared over the space background in the same location on the screen as in Experiment 1a.

The view slowly panned in random directions over the environment visible through the screen. Three different backgrounds were used. The first was a “training environment” that appeared as if the participant’s craft was inside of a large, green, wire-frame cube with green square grid lines on each wall. The second was referred to as “Boutonia” (shown in Figure 1). It contained a large, sphinxlike rotating space station, stars, and a large blue planet to the right of the station with a sun radiating light from behind the planet. The third, referred to as “Nicholusia” (Figure 1, bottom), contained a large spiral-shaped rotating space station and a colorful star system consisting of a green ringed planet to the right of the station surrounded by stars and a yellow gaseous nebula with a sun radiating light from the left of the station. Different custom music loops played in the background in each context. The latter two contexts were counterbalanced as Contexts A and B.

Instructions were presented in a black, translucent panel that rose from the bottom of the screen and were also presented through headphones in a prerecorded female voice. The panel was retracted when the participant pressed the “M” key as instructed in the game.

Four spaceships were available to use as outcomes, and all were used in the response-training phase described below in the procedure. Each ship flew rapidly into the scene from off the screen. The first was referred to as the “Stellarian” and was an off-white colored craft that appeared from the upper left of the screen. The second was a blue saucer-shaped craft (the “Learian”) that emerged from the upper right of the screen. The third was an elongated red craft (the “Juk Destroyer”), used as the target spaceship in the conditioning phases (shown in [Figure 1](#)). It flew in from the lower right of the screen. The fourth was a gray craft resembling a seahorse (the “Luckonian”) that emerged from the lower left of the screen.

Each spaceship could be repelled by a weapon assigned to it, shown in the corners of each panel in [Figure 1](#). The Stellarian was repelled by a weapon in the upper left of the screen that emitted orange fireballs, referred to as “Extinction Fire” (left “tab” key). The Learian was repelled by a weapon in the upper right of the screen that fired glowing green balls and was referred to as the “SOP Cannon” (“backspace” key). The Juk Destroyer was repelled by a weapon in the lower right of the screen, called the “Lambda Ray” (number pad “0” key). The weapon and the ray beam were both red. The Luckonian was repelled by a weapon in the lower left of the screen called the “Ibo laser” that fired multicolored cylindrical laser bolts (left “shift” key). Each bolt contained a white center surrounded by a colored glow. The glow color varied randomly between each bolt and was one of 20 different colors spanning the spectrum.

Each weapon was activated by pressing a different key, indicated in parentheses above, on the keyboard. Once 15 key presses at a rate of at least three per second had been accumulated, the weapon became active and began firing at the spaceship with every other key press, but only when the spaceship was present and a response occurred at least every 0.75 s.

Procedure

Eye-Tracking Calibration

Calibration was conducted as in [Nelson et al. \(2019\)](#), presented here with permission. Participants sat at the keyboard, headphones were placed on the participant, and they were instructed to listen and look at the screen. The position of the eye tracker was manipulated until the software indicated that the eyes were well viewed by the apparatus. The game was running

when participants were seated and they were in the training environment described earlier. The researcher sat at a table to the right of the participant behind a monitor that indicated where the participant was looking on their screen. The researcher initiated the calibration procedure from the researcher table. At the center of the participants’ screen, a torus-shaped ring (60 pixels in diameter) appeared with a small sphere in the center. The color of the sphere rapidly oscillated to give the appearance of extremely rapid flashing. Participants were instructed by a prerecorded voice through the headphones to fixate on the center of the ring and to follow it with their eyes if it moved. The software then presented the ring in nine different positions on the screen, determined by the SMI eye tracker software, and recorded gaze fixations for each to determine the eye-to-screen mapping. After that, the ring was presented again in the center of the screen from left to right and two thirds of the way down on the screen for 10 s as an accuracy check. The researcher observed the position of the participant’s gaze, and if they judged the calibration to be poor (e.g., none of the positions indicated by the eye tracker were within the ring target), the calibration was repeated until no further subjective improvements in accuracy could be obtained.

Accuracy Checks

Eye position data were recorded during the final 8 s of the accuracy check described above to have a record of the initial accuracy of the eye tracking. At the end of the game, the torus was once again presented for 10 s, and the eye position data were recorded during the final 8 s.

Outcome-Response Training

Following the calibration, when the participant was ready to start they pressed the “B” key initiating the experiment. Participants were instructed that they must learn to activate weapons to repel invading spaceships and received practice trials with all four of the different ships. On the first trial with a particular ship, the instructions informed the participant of the name of the ship, the weapon used to repel it, and the key to press to activate the weapon. They were instructed that the key must be pressed rapidly and repeatedly. The participant was then left to press the key and discover the effort necessary to activate the weapon. The ship was repelled after firing eight shots. An instruction screen then appeared congratulating the participants and reminding them of the weapon to use on that ship. On subsequent appearances of the ship, no instructions were provided. The ship simply appeared and remained flying on the screen until the participant repelled it. Participants were trained to respond to the four different spaceships (five trials each) in the

sequence described in the “response training” phase of Experiment 2 in Nelson et al. (2014). This phase took place in the training environment described earlier.

After the final response training trial, participants were informed that they were ready for patrol. The final instructions encouraged participants to have the weapons ready if they thought invaders were going to appear so that they might attack the invader upon its arrival before it attacked the space station. They were then told that invaders might appear or that they may pass their patrol enjoying “the beauty of the galaxies and music beamed from the stations” without invaders. They pressed the “M” key to proceed and were virtually transported to the galaxy where the experimental manipulations took place. They received no information regarding the sensors.

Pre-Exposure

Participants in groups same and different received six trials where the red sensor was illuminated for 20 s with no other events occurring. The intertrial interval was variable and averaged 20 s. During this phase, they experienced trials in both Contexts A and B in the order ABAB or BABA. There were three trials with the red sensor in each exposure to Context A in group same and three trials with the red sensor in each exposure to Context B in group different. Exposure to the alternate contexts was of the same duration, but a black sensor was presented on the trials, which produced no change in the display. Participants in group control received the same context exposure but no exposure to the sensor (i.e., black sensors). Changes in contexts occurred, as described in Nelson et al. (2014, Experiment 3), with a brief message informing the participants that they were to patrol another galaxy, followed by an animated sequence as if the participant’s vessel was traveling through a “wormhole” to the new galaxy.

Conditioning

Conditioning took place in Context A where pre-exposure took place in group same and was a different context than pre-exposure in group different. There were 10 trials where the red sensor was illuminated for 20 s, with the Juk Destroyer appearing after 5 s and exiting 15 s later with the sensor offset. The intertrial interval was variable around a mean of 20 s.

Data Analysis

Keyboard Responses

The computer recorded the number of responses made on the number pad zero “0” key during each second of the sensor. Analysis of the first 5 s of responding, prior to the arrival of the spaceship, was used to assess conditioning.

Eye Screening

We used the same procedures and screening as did Nelson et al. (2019), adapted here with permission. Sixty data points for each second of recording were obtained for each eye of each participant, representing the x/y coordinates of where the participant was looking. The data were scanned for missing values, and these were replaced by linear interpolation based on the time between the last and next valid recording. In cases where data were missing at the beginning or ending of a recording period, interpolation between two points was not possible. In those cases, the change in gaze direction was recorded between every pair of neighboring points in time for the period, and an average “change vector” was obtained for the participant. The closest valid data point was found (i.e., the first when data were missing at the beginning of a period and the last when data were missing at the end of a period), and the missing data were filled in by adding or subtracting the change vector to that point. For example, three missing data points would be filled in at the end of a time period by $\text{last_point} + \text{change_vector}$, $\text{last_point} + 2 \times \text{change_vector}$, $\text{last_point} + 3 \times \text{change_vector}$. The left and right eye data were then averaged to determine the final gaze position.

At the start of both accuracy checks, participants could be looking elsewhere on the screen, despite a 2-s delay between the appearance of the target and the onset of recording. Thus, some of the gaze points might represent both where the participant was looking immediately prior to the check and the path of their eyes as they located the focus point. The accuracy checks were used to correct for any systematic inaccuracy in the eye tracking; thus, we used the procedure described next to eliminate those miscellaneous points in the calculation of the center of the participants’ gaze on the accuracy checks. Because of the explicit instructions “focus on the dot,” we assumed that the majority of each participant’s gaze points should be at that point. For each accuracy check independently, we counted the number of looks at each pixel of the screen. Then, these totals were smoothed by adding to each pixel containing hits the sum of its neighbors (20-pixel radius) weighted by a Gaussian falloff function ($S = 6$). The pixel containing the largest value was obtained, and each pixel count was then expressed as a percentage of that maximum. Pixels that were looked at 50% of the maximum or higher were used to calculate the center (average x coordinate, average y coordinate) of the gaze points on the accuracy check. For each participant, the center of their fixation group for each accuracy check was expressed as a deviation vector from the true center of each on-screen focus point (true center-gaze focus point coordinates). Each deviation vector (from each accuracy check)

was negated to create a correction vector, a vector that when added to each point would adjust the center of the participant's accuracy check points to the true centers of the on-screen focus points. Every point in the participant's data was then adjusted by a vector that was itself a linear interpolation between the two correction vectors based on the point's placement in time between the first and second accuracy checks.

Fixations are typically defined by points that are within a particular radius of space within a given period of time. As these values can contain varying degrees of arbitrariness, we made no attempt at computing and analyzing fixations. Rather, we simply worked with the number of points observed within an area of interest within specified periods of time (i.e., seconds). We analyzed the amount of time gaze that was recorded in the various areas of interest (defined below). As each point represents a time sample of 1/60 of a second, the number of observations represents the seconds spent looking in an area when divided by 60.

Participants for which 10% or more of their data were interpolated were excluded. The average and standard deviations of the deviation vector lengths were calculated. Participants with deviations over 2 standard deviations from the average on either the first or second accuracy check were excluded.

Areas of Interest

We used the same areas-of-interest definitions as were used by Nelson et al. (2019). Areas of interest were defined as the sensor, outcome zone near, outcome zone far, other zone near, and other zone far. These are illustrated in the bottom panel of Figure 1. The sensor was a circular area with a liberal radius of 75 pixels centered around the middle top sensor. The outcome zones refer to the right side of the screen where the spaceship appeared. The other zones were on the left side of the screen. The outcome and other zones were divided into near and far areas, referring to the distance from the screen center. Each area ran from the top of the screen to the bottom. Near areas were nearer to the center of the screen and extended 320 pixels out from the screen center. Far areas began at the edge of the near area farthest from screen center and extended to the screen edge. The near areas were constructed in a manner to exclude the area occupied by the sensor area. These are shown in Figure 1, bottom panel, as the circular and rectangular outlines on the screen outlined in orange.

Analysis

Analysis of both the keyboard response counts and the time spent with gaze in an area were conducted with analysis of variance (ANOVA), and follow-up analyses were conducted with ANOVA using pooled error terms appropriately derived from the

overall ANOVA (see Howell, 1987). In cases where responding was extremely low, with multiple cases of zero responses among participants, data were analyzed with nonparametric statistics. Exact probabilities are reported for the reader, and the Benjamini Hochberg (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) procedure was used to control the false discovery rate when performing many pairwise comparisons. Effect sizes are reported as partial eta squared (η_p^2). Power analyses and 90% confidence intervals were calculated with software written for Microsoft Excel found in Nelson (2016). Confidence intervals are reported in brackets following the effect size. When a range of effect sizes is reported, the confidence interval represents the lower limit on the smallest value and the upper limit on the largest. In places where confidence intervals are not reported, the distributions had many degrees of freedom, and their resulting flat shape made their accurate calculation impossible due to precision limitations.

Results

Key Pressing

Key pressing occurred weakly in the pre-exposure phase in the groups that received pre-exposure to the sensor light. During conditioning, key pressing emerged in all groups but did so more slowly in the pre-exposed groups than in the control. The context switch between pre-exposure and conditioning had the opposite effect of what was expected. Responding in group different was less vigorous than responding in group same. The following analyses support these conclusions.

Pre-Exposure

Groups same and different received the exact same treatment in this phase, so we collapsed over them as group "exposed" to contrast against group control. Responding during the 20-s sensor was analyzed in 5-s blocks (see Figure 2) with a series of Mann-Whitney U tests as responding was very low (note the expanded y-axis scale of Figure 2) with multiple zeros. Of the 24 comparisons, there were five with $p \leq .05$, occurring on Blocks 1 and 2 of Trial 1, Block 1 of Trial 2, and Blocks 1 and 2 of Trial 3 ($p_{\text{range}} = .006-.048$). The Benjamini-Hochberg (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) procedure applied to the 24 comparisons, however, indicated no differences with a false discovery rate at .05 (minimum p necessary = .0021).

Conditioning

The responses per second on each of the first 5 s of the sensor, prior to the arrival of the outcome, were analyzed with a Group (control, same, different) x Experiment (1a, 1b, 1c) x Trials x Seconds ANOVA. The data are shown in Figure 3. The data broken down by experiment are shown in Figure 1 in the online supplemental

Figure 2

Average Responses per Second in 5-s Blocks During the Six 20-s Pre-Exposure Trials

Note. Open symbols show groups same and different combined. Closed symbols show the control group during the same period of time. Note the expanded y-axis.

Figure 3

Responses per Second on Each of the First 5 s of Each Trial of Conditioning

Note. Group control received no pre-exposure to the sensor. Groups same and different received pre-exposure to the sensor in either the same or different context as conditioning, respectively. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean. Different colored/shaded symbols indicate differences where $p < .05$.

materials. As the degrees of freedom for the numerator and denominator of the effects tested vary across tests, the power varied by test. To detect purely between-subjects effects, power ranged from .23 to .31 for small effects (i.e., $\eta_p^2 = .01$), ranged from .85 to .9 for medium effects ($\eta_p^2 = .06$), and was 1 for large effects ($\eta_p^2 = .14$). Power to detect within-subject and mixed between-within-subject effect power ranged from .63 to 1 for

small effects, ranged from .85 to 1 for medium effects, and was 1 for large effects.

Of most relevance in this initial analysis, there was an Experiment x Trials interaction, $F(18, 1836) = 1.76, p = .02, \eta_p^2 = .017, 90\% \text{ CI } [.001, .02]$, mean square error (MSE) = 7.96, that did not interact with group, $F = 1$. There was also a Seconds x Experiment interaction, $F(8, 816) = 2.64, p = .03, \eta_p^2 = .026 [.004, .04]$, MSE = 4.05, that did not interact with group, $F(16, 816) = 1.34, p = .16$. Simple effects (MSE = 1.53) showed that responding on Trial 1 was slightly lower in Experiment 1 ($\bar{x} = .18$) than in Experiment 2 ($\bar{x} = .64$), $F(1, 565) = 5.1, p = .02, \eta_p^2 = .033 [.002, .09]$. Experiments 1 and 2 did not differ on any other trial, $ps = .06$. Experiment 3 showed somewhat more responding than Experiments 1 and 2 combined on Trials 2–4 (Experiments 1 and 2 $\bar{x}s = 1.21, 2.07, 2.76$; Experiment 3 $\bar{x}s = 1.91, 2.89, 3.53$) and on Trials 6–7 (Experiments 1 and 2 $\bar{x}s = 3.42, 3.79$; Experiment 3 $\bar{x}s = 3.84, 4.35$), $Fs(1, 565) = 5.08, p_{\text{range}} = .00005-.024, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .04-.09 [.001, .14]$. These differences were minor and did not interact with the group manipulation. Elimination of the experiment variable (i.e., consigning it to the error variance) did not affect any of the other effects in the analysis; thus, the experiment variable was discarded for simplicity in the remaining presentation and analysis of key pressing.

The Group x Trials x Seconds analysis of the conditioning data showed effects of group, $F(2, 210) = 31.29, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .23, 90\% \text{ CI } [.15, .30]$, MSE = 101.35; trials, $F(9, 1890) = 216.72, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .51 [.48, .53]$, MSE = 8.00; and Trials x Group, $F(18, 1890) = 7.64, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .07 [.04, .08]$. All effects involving seconds and its interaction with trials, group, and Trials x Group were reliable, $ps < .00001, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .04-.69 [.02, .71]$, $MSE_{\text{seconds}} = 4.12, MSE_{\text{Trials} \times \text{Seconds}} = 1.07$. As shown in Figure 3, group control clearly outperformed groups same and different, and group same appears to have outperformed group different, contrary to the normal effect of a context change.

Simple pairwise group comparisons on each second of each trial (MSE = 4.56, Degrees of Freedom (df) = 999) indicated 91 differences with $p < .05$. Those are shown in Figure 3 by different colored symbols. Group control clearly outperformed groups same and different. There were differences among groups same and different during the middle part of conditioning. Group same outperformed group different on Trial 4, Seconds 2–5, $Fs = 4.34, p_{\text{range}} = .008-.036, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .03-.067, 90\% \text{ CI } [.001, .14]$; Trial 5, Seconds 4 and 5, $Fs = 4, p_{\text{range}} = .03-.046, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .027-.03 [.00001, .1]$; and Trial 6, Seconds 2, 3, and 5, $Fs = 3.99, p_{\text{range}} = .02-.046, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .027-.035 [.00003, .1]$. Applying the Benjamini-Hochberg (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) procedure to the 150 comparisons confirmed the same general conclusions, identifying

81 differences, including same versus different differences on Trial 4 (Seconds 2, 4, and 5) and Trial 6 (Second 3). Among the 41 s where group same versus group different differences occurred with $p > .05$, group same responded numerically more than group different 37 times, which is not what would be expected by chance (two-tailed binomial $p = 1.026 \times 10^7$).

Eye-Gaze Data

Our screening procedures eliminated 37 participants from the eye data. There were 20 in each group remaining in Experiment 1a; 21, 20, and 21 in groups control, same, and different, respectively, in Experiment 1b; and 18 in each group in Experiment 1c. Exclusion was unrelated to group or experiment, $X^2 \leq 2.65$, $ps = .26$. Participants looked less within each trial at the flashing sensor in Experiment 1a, where the sensor apparatus was always present and embedded in a control panel (Figure 1, top), than did participants in Experiments 1b and 1c, where both the appearance of the sensor apparatus and its flashing were novel. Nevertheless, the main conclusions of interest were not affected by that difference. During pre-exposure, looking at the sensor decreased within and between trials in the pre-exposed groups. During conditioning, the control group looked at the sensor more than did the pre-exposed conditions, and looking decreased over trials in all groups. There was no restoration of looking with a context change.

When gazing at the rest of the screen, participants came to direct their gaze to the area where the spaceship outcome would arrive, and this goal-tracking effect was more pronounced in the control group than in the same and different groups. The effect was more pronounced in the different group than the same group, suggesting that the acquisition of goal tracking was retarded by pre-exposing the sensor and that, unlike what was observed in the key-press data, a context change attenuated that effect.

Analysis of gazing at the sensor and outcome zones, in conjunction with the key-press data, showed that gaze shifted from sign tracking to goal tracking along conditioning. Key pressing was not strongly related to the eye-tracking measures, though it did correlate with sign tracking, goal tracking, and the shift from sign to goal tracking.

Pre-Exposure

There were no differences between Experiments 1b and 1c, where the sensor appeared on the space background. Both differed from Experiment 1a where the sensor apparatus was present in a control panel. Our analyses below include the control panel variable, which was collapsed over Experiments 1b and c (where the control panel is absent) to contrast against Experiment 1a (where the control panel was present).

In pre-exposure, we collapsed across groups same and different as they received the same treatment. The control group received no pre-exposure to the sensor, and any looks at the sensor apparatus (control panel present) or the area where the sensor would have been present (control panel absent) would be spurious glances or saccades and was very low. The time spent in the sensor area averaged .023 s (range 0–.1) in the control panel-present experiment and .028 s (range .0005–.09) in the control-panel-absent experiments.

The data from the exposed conditions (shown in Figure 4) were analyzed with a Control Panel (present, absent) x Trials x Seconds ANOVA. For purely between-subjects effects, power was at .26 for small effects, .91 for medium effects, and 1 for large effects. For within-subject and mixed between-within effects, power in this analysis ranged from .61 to 1 for small effects and was 1 for medium and large effects. Effects involving seconds could be detected with a power of .8 as low as .0062 and involving Trials x Seconds as low as .002.

There was a Control Panel x Trials x Seconds interaction, $F(95, 16530) = 1.56$, $p = .0004$, $MSE_{\text{Trials} \times \text{Seconds}} = .05$, though it was quite small, $\eta_p^2 = .0095$. No other effects, not superseded by the interaction, were reliable, $ps \geq .84$. The patterns regarding the control panel variable are clear without further analysis. Illuminating the sensor produced roughly the same initial orienting during the first second both with and without the control panel. The looks declined during the illumination but did so more slowly when both the sensor apparatus and its illumination suddenly appeared (control panel absent) than when the visible sensor apparatus was simply illuminated (control panel present).

With the control panel present, there was a Trials x Seconds interaction, $F(95, 16530) = 1.41$, $p = .006$, $\eta_p^2 = .035$, superseding all other effects. The effect of seconds was present on every trial, $F_s(19, 16530) = 4.02$, $ps < .0001$, $MSE = .056$, with effect sizes decreasing from $\eta_p^2 = .22$, 90% CI [.16, .24], on Trial 1 to $\eta_p^2 = .09$ [.04, .1] on Trial 6. Overall gazing at the sensor decreased between Trials 1 and 2, $F(1, 870) = 12.84$, $p = .0004$, $MSE = .014$, $\eta_p^2 = .25$ [.07, .41]. There were no other decreases between trials, $ps = .11$.

With the control panel absent, there was also a Trials x Seconds interaction, $F(19, 16530) = 3.29$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .04$, superseding all other effects. The effect of seconds was present on every trial, $F_s(19, 16530) = 4.11$, $ps \leq .0001$, with the effect size ranging from $\eta_p^2 = .05$, 90% CI [.02, .06], on Trial 2 to $\eta_p^2 = .15$ [.12, .17] on Trial 6. Gazing at the sensor decreased from Trials 1 to 2 and 2 to 3 and slightly increased from Trial 3 to Trial 4 before decreasing between Trials 4 and 5, $F_s(1, 870) = 6.24$, $ps \leq .0001$, $\eta_p^2_{\text{range}} =$

.08–.33 [.008, .45]. There was no change between Trials 5 and 6, $F < 1$.

Conditioning

The data from looking at the sensor during conditioning are shown in Figure 5. The control group looked at the sensor more than the same and different groups on the first trial and tended to maintain more attention to the CS during the later seconds of each trial than did the same and different groups. The control group showed the largest change over trials between Trials 1 and 2. With one exception, the remaining significant changes were overall decreases in looking. The same and different groups never differed from each other in looking at the sensor. The context change produced no restoration of the orienting that had habituated during pre-exposure. An increase in orienting could be expected with a context change as habituation has been shown to be affected by context change (e.g., Chiandetti & Turatto, 2017; Evans & Hammond, 1983; Jordan et al., 2000; Kruse et al., 2004; Rankin, 2000; Tomsic et al., 1998; Wagner, 1981), but there are multiple good examples where it has not (e.g., Hall & Channell, 1985; Hall & Honey, 1989; Marlin & Miller, 1981; see Hall & Rodríguez, 2020, for a review). As opposed to the conditioning restoring a habituated orienting response, there was no increase in orienting in the pre-exposed groups between Trials 1 and 2, nor thereafter. With one exception, all further significant changes were decreases.

Figure 4
Seconds Gazing at the Sensor During Each Second (1 to 20) of the Pre-Exposure Trials in Experiment 1a With the Control Panel Present (Figure 1 Top) and in Experiments 1b and 1c With the Control Panel Absent (Figure 1 Bottom)

Note. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean.

When not looking at the sensor, the participants looked at the rest of the screen, with most of that gaze directed to the outcome zone where the spaceship was expected. In the far areas of the outcome zone, there was an effect of pre-exposure, where pre-exposure in the same context reduced the tendency to goal track,

while pre-exposure in the different context had no effect. These descriptions are supported by the following analyses.

Gazing at the Sensor. Time spent with gaze in the sensor area was analyzed with a Group x Control Panel x Trials x Seconds ANOVA. Power to detect purely between-subject effects ranged from .2 to .25 for small effects, ranged from .85 to .9 for medium, and was 1 for large effects. For within and mixed between-within effects, power ranged from .41 to .99 for small effects and was .99 or above for medium and large effects.

Figure 5
Seconds Gazing at the Sensor on Each of the First 5 s of Each Trial of Conditioning

Note. Group control received no pre-exposure to the sensor. Groups same and different received pre-exposure to the sensor in either the same or different context as conditioning, respectively. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean.

First, we will dispense with the control panel effect. There was an effect of the control panel and a Control Panel x Seconds interaction, $F(4, 680) = 5.72, p = .0001, MSE_{seconds} = .099, \eta_p^2 = .03, 90\% CI [.01, .05]$ (shown in Figure 6, right), that reflects what was seen in pre-exposure. Looking at the sensor declined more rapidly when it was in the control panel. There were no other effects involving the control panel.

There was a Group x Seconds interaction (shown in Figure 6, left) where the control group looked at the sensor longer over its presentation than did the same and different groups, $F(8, 680) = 2.14, p = .03, MSE_{seconds} = .06, \eta_p^2 = .025, 90\% CI [.001, .035]$, when averaged over trials. There was a Trials x Seconds interaction, $F(36, 6120) = 1.58, p = .015, MSE_{Trials \times Seconds} = .059, \eta_p^2 = .009$, as the effect of seconds overall grew slightly more pronounced over trials.

There was a Group x Trials interaction, $F(18, 1530) = 1.86, p = .015, MSE_{trials} = .18, \eta_p^2 = .02, 90\% CI [.002, .022]$. As is evident in Figure 5, there were clear group differences on Trial 1 where the control group saw the sensor for the first time. There were no

other reliable effects that were not superseded by one of the interactions reported above.

The same analysis of only the pre-exposed groups showed that there were no effects involving group (context), $ps = .21$. The effect of trials was reliable, $F(9, 1530) = 2.57, p = .006, \eta_p^2 = .02, 90\% \text{ CI } [.003, .03]$. Comparing each trial to the subsequent trial showed an overall decrease in orienting to the light between Trials 1 and 2 and between Trials 8 and 9 and a small increase between Trials 9 and 10, $F_s(1, 1530) = 8.49, ps = .004, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .068-.1 [.01, .19]$. There was no restoration of orienting to the light when responding had been acquired, as was observed by [Kaye and Pearce \(1984, 1987\)](#).

The analysis of the control condition showed an effect of trials, $F(9, 1530) = 10.06, p = .0001, \eta_p^2 = .15, 90\% \text{ CI } [.09, .18]$. Comparisons between adjacent trials showed decreases between Trials 1 and 2, 5 and 6, and 8 and 9 and an increase from Trial 6 to 7, $F_s(1, 1530) = 6.75, ps \leq .009, \eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .1-.56 [.01, .65]$.

Gazing at the Screen. When not gazing at the sensor, participants were gazing at the rest of the screen. Because looking at the screen and looking at the sensor compromise the total amount of time gazing, effects of seconds would simply be the inverse of those already analyzed while gazing at the sensor. We used the same analysis strategy as [Nelson et al. \(2019\)](#) and collapsed across the seconds variable on each trial in the analysis of gazing at the rest of the screen. The data are shown in [Figure 7](#). The data shown broken down by experiment are in [Figure 2](#) of the [online supplemental materials](#). The figure shows the three groups' (along the x-axis) looks at the outcome zone (solid circles) and other zone (open circles) in the near (top panel) and far (bottom panel) areas.

Gazing at the screen during conditioning was analyzed with a Group x Control Panel x Zone (Outcome or other) x Depth (near or far) x Trials ANOVA. To detect purely between-subjects effects, the ranges of power were the same as in the analysis of gazing at the sensor. To detect within and mixed between-within effects, the power ranged between .2 and .79 for small effects, ranged between .85 and 1 for medium effects, and was 1 for large effects.

There was a Control Panel x Zone x Depth interaction, $F(1, 170) = 4.31, \text{MSE}_{\text{Zone} \times \text{Depth}} = .04, p = .039, \eta_p^2 = .025, 90\% \text{ CI } [.000, .07]$. There were no other effects involving control panel that were not superseded by this interaction. The Zone x Depth interaction was present in both groups with the control panel present, $F(1, 170) = 16.82, p < .0001$, and without the control panel, $F(1, 170) = 4.60, p = .03$. The effect was simply larger with the panel $\eta_p^2 = .23 [.08, .37]$ than without, $\eta_p^2 = .07 [.002, .2]$. The

Figure 6
Seconds Gazing At The Sensor On Each Second Of Each Trial Collapsed Across Trials Presented By Group (Left) Or By The Control Panel Presence/Absence (Right)

Note. Top panel shows seconds gazing at the outcome zone or other zone averaged across the first 5 s of each trial of conditioning. Group control received no pre-exposure to the sensor. Groups same and different received pre-exposure to the sensor in either the same or different context as conditioning, respectively. Top panel (near) shows gazing near the middle of the screen (middle 6 25% minus the sensor), and the bottom panel shows gazing in the far areas of the screen. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Zone x Depth interaction is the result of people looking more at the Outcome zone than the other zone, with that difference being more prevalent in the near than in the far area. The effects of zone and depth are analyzed in the following paragraph with respect to a significant four-way interaction.

There was a Group x Zone x Depth x Trials interaction, $F(18, 1530) = 1.67, p < .0001, \text{MSE}_{\text{Zone} \times \text{Depth} \times \text{Trials}} = .02, \eta_p^2 = .02, 90\% \text{ CI } [0, .2]$. There were no other effects interpreted that were not superseded by this interaction or the one reported in the previous paragraph, $ps = .06$. The four-way interaction was investigated by examining the Group x Zone x Trials interaction within each depth level. In the near area, there was no Group x

Zone x Trials interaction, $p = .43$. As shown clearly in the figure, a preference for looking toward the outcome zone emerged quickly in all groups when looking to the near areas of the screen (nearer the center). In the far area, there was a Group x Zone x Trials interaction, $F(18, 1530) = 1.78$, $p = .023$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$ [.001, .021]. The error bars make it evident where significant differences between the zones would be found and suggest the effect of zone was larger in the control and different groups than in the same group, particularly toward the end of training. To investigate that pattern, we calculated the differences in looking time between the outcome and other zone and then examined the effect of group on that variable on each trial (i.e., we examined Zone x Group interactions on each trial). The preference for the outcome

Figure 7
Seconds Gazing on Each Trial In Near (Top Panel) And Far (Bottom Panel) Outcome and Other Zones

Note. Left panel: Seconds gazing at the sensor on each of the first 5 s of each trial of conditioning collapsed across trials. Group control received no pre-exposure to the sensor. Groups same and different received pre-exposure to the sensor in either the same or different context as conditioning, respectively. Right panel: Seconds gazing at the sensor on each of the first 5 s of each trial of conditioning collapsed across Experiment 1a, with the control panel present, and

² The eye-tracking and keyboard response measures were collected in different files on different computers with different file names over several weeks to months for each experiment. While it was an easy matter to determine which group each file belonged to, matching the eye-tracking data to the behavioral response data on an individual basis required matching the data files by their collection times that were recorded within the files. Though their settings were close, neither computer was connected to the internet whereby they would be synced to a common clock. Moreover, one was apparently set to

zone over the other zone was weaker in the same group than in both the control, Trials 7, 8, and 10, $F_s(1, 2792)_{\text{range}} = 5.51\text{--}24.51$, $p_{\text{range}} = 7.8 \times 10^{-7}\text{--}.018$, $MSE = .012$, $\eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .056\text{--}.18$ [.004, .27], and different groups, Trials 7–10, $F_s(1, 2792)_{\text{range}} = 4.62\text{--}28.83$, $p_{\text{range}} = 8.6 \times 10^{-8}\text{--}.03$, $MSE = .012$, $\eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .03\text{--}.20$ [.002, .30]. Goal tracking was reduced with pre-exposure, and a context change attenuated that effect.

Gaze and Keyboard Responding Relations. We further analyzed the data with respect to the relationships between the different eye-tracking measures and the keyboard responding for 161 of the participants.² For each participant, we standardized the time spent looking at the sensor, the outcome zone (sum of outcome near and far areas), and the keyboard responses across the 10 conditioning trials. We also calculated the difference between gazing in the outcome zone and gazing at the sensor as a measure of the shift from sign to goal tracking and standardized that variable. Correlation coefficients and regression slopes were calculated between these variables for each participant. Analyses of these correlations between groups were done on Fisher's z transformation of the individual correlations.

Of the 161 participants with matched data, all but 11 participants showed a shift from sign (looking at the sensor) to goal (looking into the outcome zone) tracking (i.e., -r) across the trials. The correlation averaged ($r = .13$) among those 11 participants who did not show a shift. The distribution of those 11 participants was not independent of group, with none being from the control group, eight from group same, and three from group different, $\chi^2(2) = 9.04$, $p = .01$. Among the pre-exposed conditions, the distribution of the participants was independent of the two groups, $p = .11$.

Sensor and Outcome Zone

There was a negative average correlation between gazing at the sensor and outcome zones, $r_{\text{mean}} = -.64$, $F(1, 158) = 318.35$, $p = .0001$, $MSE_{\text{between}} = .28$, $\eta_p^2 = .68$, 90% CI [.6, .71], and an effect of group, $F(2, 158) = 4.10$, $p = .018$, $\eta_p^2 = .05$ [.005, .11]. The strength of the relationship was stronger in the control group ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.72$) than in group same ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.55$), $F(1, 158) = 7.98$, $p = .005$, $\eta_p^2 = .07$ [.018, .16]. Responding in group different ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.62$) hovered between the other two groups, not differing reliably

adjust for daylight savings time changes, and the other was not. The eye-tracking data creation times within the files were when the file was initially created, when the tracker was set up sometime prior to the subject's arrival. The keyboard response data were written at the end of the experimental session. With these complications producing discrepancies between the times recorded in the different file types, we were able to confidently match the data for 161 of the 176 participants analyzed previously.

from either the control, $F(1, 158) = 3.45, p = .065$, or pre-exposed same condition, $F < 1$.

Analyzing the beta coefficients showed an average increase of .64 standard deviations in outcome-zone gazing for every standard deviation decrease in gazing at the sensor, $F(1, 158) = 243.81, p < .0001, MSE_{\text{between}} = .27, \eta_p^2 = .61, 90\% \text{ CI } [.53, .66]$, with differences between the groups, $F(2, 158) = 4.3, p = .015, \eta_p^2 = .05 [.006, .11]$. The control ($b_{\text{mean}} = -.75$) and group different ($b_{\text{mean}} = -.68$) did not differ, $F < 1$, and both differed from group same ($b_{\text{mean}} = -.47$), $F_s(1, 158) = 7.84$ and $4.53, p = .008$ and $.03, \eta_p^2 = .07 [.018, .16]$ and $.04 [.001, .11]$, for comparisons with group control and group different, respectively. These data show that the magnitude of the shift from sign to goal tracking differed by group, being weakest in group same, and are consistent with the analysis of the goal-tracking response itself presented earlier, particularly into the far area of the outcome zone.

Tracking Shift and Keyboard Responding

The average correlation between the shift from sign to goal tracking (outcome zone minus sensor) with the acquisition of the keyboard response was positive, $r_{\text{mean}} = .25, F(1, 158) = 62.14, p, .0001, MSE_{\text{between}} = .17, \eta_p^2 = .28, 90\% \text{ CI } [.19, .37]$, with no effect of group, $F = 1, (r = .29, .19, .26$ for groups control, pre-exposed same, and pre-exposed different, respectively). The analysis of b showed that there was a 1.28 standard deviation increase in keyboard responding for every standard deviation increase in the shift to goal tracking, $F(2, 158) = 51.59, p < .0001, MSE_{\text{between}} = 5.13, \eta_p^2 = .25 [.15, .33]$, but that did not differ by group, $F < 1$ ($b = 1.37, 1.26$, and 1.22 for groups control, same, and different, respectively).

Sign Tracking and Keyboard Responding

The correlation between gazing at the sensor and responding on the keyboard was negative, $r_{\text{mean}} = -.17, F(1, 158) = 21.44, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .12, 90\% \text{ CI } [.05, .2], MSE = .21$, and there were group differences, $F(2, 158) = 4.65, p = .01, \eta_p^2 = .05 [.007, .12]$. Groups control ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.29$) and same ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.03$) differed, $F(1, 158) = 9.3, p = .002, \eta_p^2 = .08 [.02, .18]$, but group different ($r_{\text{mean}} = -.16$) did not differ from either the control, $F(1, 158) = 1.42, p = .24$, or same group, $F < 1$. The analysis of b for the sensor/keyboard response regression showed an overall average increase of 2.16 standard deviations in keyboard responding for every 1 standard deviation decrease in sensor gazing, $F(1, 158) = 5.92, p = .01, MSE_{\text{between}} = 127.83, \eta_p^2 = .036 [.003, .09]$, with no group differences ($b_{\text{mean}} = -3.06, 0.29$, and -3.71 for groups same and different, respectively), $F(2, 158) = 1.99, p = .14$.

Goal Tracking and Keyboard Responding

Looks into the outcome zone and the keyboard response showed a positive correlation, $r_{\text{mean}} = .27, F(1, 158) = 79.789, p <$

$.0001, MSE_{\text{between}} = .16, \eta_p^2 = .33, 90\% \text{ CI } [.24, .42]$. There was no effect of group, $F < 1$ ($r_{\text{mean}} = .24, .26$, and $.32$ for groups control, same, and different, respectively). The analysis of the outcome zone/keyboard response regression coefficients revealed an overall average increase of 2.34 standard deviations in keyboard responding for every standard deviation increase in outcome zone gazing, $F(1, 158) = 62.16, p < .0001, MSE_{\text{between}} = 14.16, \eta_p^2 = .28 [.19, .37]$, with no differences between the groups, $F(2, 158) = 1.09, p = .34$ ($b_{\text{mean}} = 1.74, 2.81$, and 2.46 for groups control, same, and different, respectively).

As participants came to expect the outcome, gaze shifted from the sign to the goal area as indicated by the negative correlation between sensor and outcome zone gazing over trials. Moreover, the rate of change was predictive between the groups, being least in group same and equal in groups control and different conditions, paralleling the keyboard responding. However, the relationship of the shift to goal tracking with the keyboard response was certainly not complete ($r^2_{\text{mean}} = .167$), nor was the relationship between the keyboard responding and either gazing at the sensor or gazing at the outcome alone ($r^2_{\text{mean}} = .164$ and $.167$, respectively). These modest relations indicate that although gaze responses and keyboard responses may share a common mechanism, different factors are also likely to be involved.

Sign and Goal Trackers

Although all but 11 participants showed an increase in goal tracking over trials, at the end of training, participants still differed with respect to whether they were attending more to the sensor or the outcome zone. To differentiate them, we constructed a "tracking ratio" of looks in the outcome zone divided by the sum of looks in the outcome zone and looks at the sensor on the last trial. The last trial is least likely to be affected by, or reflect, differences in conditioning rates between the groups. Participants looking equally at the two zones would have scores of .5 (there were no scores of exactly .5), while those looking more at the outcome zone or sensor zone have ratios above or below .5, respectively. We categorized participants as sign or goal trackers based on whether their tracking ratio was above or below .5.

There were 52 sign trackers (16, 22, and 14 in groups control, same, and different, respectively) and 109 goal trackers (35, 33, and 41 in groups control, same, and different, respectively). Tracking categorization was independent of grouping, $\chi^2(2) = 2.69, p = .26$. The tracking ratio itself did not differ between the groups, $F < 1$.

Responding on the Keyboard

Responding on the keyboard, averaged across the 5 s of the cue presentation before the outcome, is shown in Figure 8, broken down by group and tracking style. A Tracker (sign or goal) x Group x Trials ANOVA of these data showed no overall effect of tracking, $F(1, 155) = 2.63, p = .11$, but there was a Group x Tracker interaction, $F(2, 155) = 4.45, p = .01, \eta_p^2 = .05, 90\% \text{ CI } [.006, .11], \text{MSE}_{\text{between}} = 18.11$, as well as a three-way interaction with trials, $F(18, 1395) = 1.63, p = .045, \eta_p^2 = .02 [0, .021], \text{MSE}_{\text{trials}} = 1.595$. When broken down by group, the interaction was clearly produced by differences in the same and different groups. In the control group, there was no effect of tracker and no interaction with trials, $p_s = .21$. A Group x Tracker x Trials ANOVA of the same and different groups produced a two-way interaction of Group x Tracker, $F(1, 155) = 8.53, p = .004, \eta_p^2 = .07 [.01, .16]$, and a three-way interaction with trials, $F(9, 1395) = 2.52, p = .007, \eta_p^2 = .02 [.003, .03]$. There was no effect whatsoever of group, $F = .002$, with respect to these two groups.

Figure 8

Mean Responses per Second in Each Group on Each Trial of Conditioning

Note. The left panel shows participants categorized as sign trackers ($n = 52$), and the right panel shows participants categorized as goal trackers ($n = 109$). Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean.

In the prior analysis of responding, without considering the tracking style of the participants, there was an effect of group where there was less responding in group different. Here, the “correct” result, obtaining less evidence for an effect of CS pre-exposure in the different context, was apparent in the sign trackers. The opposite result, more retardation of conditioning, was apparent in the goal trackers. The effect obtained in the initial analysis, reflecting more retardation in the different context, appears to be the result of simply having more goal trackers than sign trackers in the analysis. When the sign- and

goal-tracking groups’ averages are given equal weight, the main effect of group (context) disappears.

Eye-Gaze Data

Pre-exposure. During pre-exposure, when the sensor was not being paired with the outcome, a Tracker x Trials analysis of gazing at the sensor in the pre-exposed groups showed no effect of tracker, $F(1, 108) = 1.77, p = .19$, and no interaction with trials, $F < 1$. Gazing at the sensor averaged .34 and .30 during pre-exposure for sign and goal trackers, respectively. At the time of pre-exposure, there was no preference for looking at the sensor among sign trackers over goal trackers.

Conditioning: Sign Tracking. During conditioning, with respect to tracking the sensor or outcome zones, the categorization of the participants based on looks in these areas during the last trial would create differences on that trial that could bias the main effects and interactions. Thus, the analyses of gazing in these areas by tracker excluded the final trial (it is shown in the figures). A Trials x Group x Tracker analysis of gazing at the sensor (see Figure 9) revealed what would generally be expected. There was a main effect of tracker, with sign trackers looking at the sensor more than goal trackers, $F(1, 155) = 13.61, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .08, 90\% \text{ CI } [.02, .15], \text{MSE}_{\text{between}} = .19$. There was a main effect of trials, $F(8, 1240) = 6.95, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .04 [.02, .056], \text{MSE}_{\text{trials}} = .036$, as overall gazing at the sensor tended to decrease. There was

Figure 9

Average Per-Second Gazing at the Sensor During the 10 Conditioning Trials for Sign Trackers (Left) and Goal Trackers (Right) in Groups Control (Solid Circle), Same (Open Circle), and Different (Solid Triangle)

a Trials x Group interaction, $F(16, 1240) = 1.76, p = .03, \eta_p^2 = .02 [.001, .024]$, reflecting that the control group initially looked at the sensor more than the pre-exposed groups. There were no other effects involving tracker, $p_s = .31$. The effect of trials overall

was reliable in the control group, $F(8, 1240) = 7.40, p = .007, \eta_p^2 = .13$ [.07, .17], but not in the other two groups, $F_s = 1.68, p_s = .195$.

Conditioning: Goal Tracking. We analyzed the data from looking at the far zones of the screen, where differences were detected in the prior analyses, by group and tracker. The data are shown in Figure 10. A Tracker x Zone (outcome/other) x Group x Trials ANOVA produced effects of zone, $F(1, 155) = 88.61, p < .0001, MSE_{zone} = .028, \eta_p^2 = .36, 90\% CI [.26, .45]$, but no interactions with group or tracker, $p_s = .36$. The Zone x Group x Tracker interaction approached traditional significance, $F(2, 155) = 2.71, p = .069, \eta_p^2 = .03$ [0, .08]. There was an effect of trials, $F(8, 1240) = 2.66, p = .007, \eta_p^2 = .017$ [.003, .02], $MSE_{trials} = .009$, with no interactions with group, tracker, or Group x Tracker, $p_s = .30$. There was a Zone x Trials interaction, $F(8, 1240) = 4.96, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .03$ [.01, .04], $MSE_{Zone \times Trials} = .0097$, that did not interact with group or tracker, $p_s = .35$, but the four-way interaction approached traditional significance, $F(16, 1240) = 1.63, p = .055, \eta_p^2 = .02$ [0, .022]. There were no main effects of group or tracker and no interaction, $p_s = .11$.

We had an a priori interest in the zone by group effect as it appeared in the prior set of analyses that did not include the tracker style of the participant; thus, we examined the patterns that produced the low-probability Zone x Group x Tracker effect in our sample. In the sign trackers, there was an effect of zone, $F(1, 155) = 30.21, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .38, 90\% CI [.20, .51]$, and no interaction with group, $F < 1$. In the goal trackers, there was a Zone x Group interaction, $F(1, 155) = 5.09, p = .007, \eta_p^2 = .046$ [.002, .12]. The effect of zone was present in the control and different groups, $F_s(1, 155) = 31.55, p_s < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .1$ [.05, .2], and its size did not vary between these groups, $F < 1$. The effect of zone was also present in group same, $F(1, 155) = 5.48, p = .02, \eta_p^2 = .02$ [.001, .06], but was smaller than that of both the control and different groups, $F_s = 11.87, p_s < .001, \eta_p^2 = .14$ [.03, .36].

Discussion

The experiments presented here examined the effects of stimulus pre-exposure and conditioning on the allocation of overt attention to the stimuli present in the task. The experiments replicated the procedure of Nelson et al. (2021) where participants were preexposed to a flashing light, or not, and subsequently received conditioning by pairing the light with an attacking-spaceship outcome. Among those pre-exposed to the light, the pre-exposure took place either in the same or different context as conditioning with the expectation that the effect of pre-exposure would be attenuated with a context change. Throughout this training, visual attention to the elements of the screen was monitored with an eye tracker. Following initial

analyses, an exploratory set of analyses was performed on the data including the tracking style (sign or goal) of the participants as determined by a ratio of goal tracking over sign plus goal tracking on the final conditioning trial.

During pre-exposure to the flashing light, participants first visually oriented to the light, and that orientation decreased both within and between trials. At that point, the sign-/goal-tracking style of the participant did not matter. Thus, any differences in Figure 10

Average Per-Second Gazing Into the Outcome Far (Solid Circles) or Other Far Zones (Open Circles) During Conditioning for Sign Trackers (Top) and Goal Trackers (Bottom) in Groups Control (Left), Same (Middle), and Different (Right)

later phases are unlikely to be simply because sign-tracking participants simply preferred looking at the light.

When the light was then paired with the attacking-spaceship outcome, attention to it was not restored (cf. Kaye & Pearce, 1984, 1987), nor when analyzed with respect to whether participants were sign or goal trackers. Overall, attention to the light declined, and the control group showed more attention to the light than did the pre-exposed groups. Thus, the effect of pre-exposure on attention covaried with the acquisition of the response, as would be predicted by theories that attribute the pre-exposure effect to a reduction in attention or salience (e.g., Haselgrove et al., 2010; Le Pelley, 2004; Lubow et al., 1981; Mackintosh, 1975; Pearce & Hall, 1980; Pearce & Mackintosh, 2010).

Interestingly, attention to the light decreased over conditioning, which is not expected given theories that indicate that attention should increase as the stimuli become more predictive (Le Pelley, 2004; Mackintosh, 1975). In the control group, the light was a better predictor of the outcome in conditioning, and attention was maintained better than in the pre-exposed groups. The control group did spend more time looking at the sensor in the latter part of each trial. However, the predictiveness of the stimulus is confounded with its novelty at the time of conditioning when comparing the control and pre-exposed groups. A group that received only exposure throughout both phases would be needed to eliminate the novelty confound and determine if conditioning was responsible for maintenance of any attention in either the control or pre-exposed groups.

The decline in attention to the sensor light was likely to be partly the consequence of a competition for attention between predictive stimuli and those being predicted (i.e., the spaceship). When not looking at the sensor, participants directed their gaze to the rest of the screen, with that gaze being predominately directed to the area of the screen where the expected spaceship would appear over trials. As indicated by the correlational analyses, goal tracking produced by anticipation of the outcome lowered the attention devoted to the predicting stimulus over trials. This competing goal-tracking response lessens the method's suitability for observing attentional changes to the CS, as opposed to the predictive-learning methods that have been used to assess attention to predictive cues. In those, when the outcomes appear, they occupy much the same space on the screen as the predicting stimuli. Moreover, the outcome screens are presented after the participant makes a response on a Likert-type scale. Thus, while particular cues may predict particular outcomes, the presentation of the outcome is not occasioned by the cue but by a response. Therefore, in such procedures, the cues alone may not elicit goal-tracking responses as the outcome's presentation is not expected until after a response is made.

Unlike what was observed by Nelson et al. (2021), the context change did not weaken the pre-exposure effect with respect to responding on the keyboard when considering the data as a whole. Instead, the data show that the pre-exposure effect was more robust in the different context. That observation is peculiar as we used the same method and parameters as Nelson et al. (2021) who reported the opposite result, a result that is consistent with the effects of context change on pre-exposure reported in the literature. That experiment was, like the present experiment, well powered using 148 participants. It is unlikely that the effect reported there was incorrect.

When we consider whether participants were sign or goal trackers, a different pattern emerged. Among sign trackers, the result obtained by Nelson et al. (2021) was obtained. The change of context reduced the effect of pre-exposure. Among goal trackers, the change of context increased the effect of pre-exposure. As there were more goal trackers than sign trackers, the overall effect was to observe an increase in the pre-exposure effect with a change in context.

With respect to the eye data, there were no significant differences in looking at the sensor between those who received a context change and those who did not, regardless of whether the participants were sign or goal trackers. Orienting did not recover with a context change (e.g., Hall & Channell, 1985; cf., Jordan et al., 2000), though observation of such a recovery could be interfered with by the acquisition of the goal-tracking response.

The goal-tracking response was also attenuated by pre-exposure. Unlike what was observed with the keyboard response, the context change weakened the pre-exposure effect on the goaltracking response. The goal-tracking response was acquired better with a context change between pre-exposure and conditioning than when no such change occurred. This latter observation is supported by analysis of the goal-tracking response itself, along with the regression showing the relationship between looking at the sensor and looking into the outcome zones. Looking into the outcome zone, for each decrement in looking at the sensor, increased over trials at a greater rate in both the control and different groups than in group same. Analysis of the data with respect to the tracking style of the participant showed that the attenuation of the response by pre-exposure, and its recovery with a context change, was mostly evident in the goal trackers.

The overall analysis conflicts with the data presented by Nelson et al. (2021) where a change in context produced the common finding of a lessening of the impact of pre-exposure to the cue (e.g., Byron Nelson & del Carmen Sanjuan, 2006; Hall & Channell, 1985). As sign or goal trackers could not be isolated in that experiment, it collapsed over participant's tracking style. In the present experiment, the change of context increased the pre-exposure effect on acquisition of the keyboard response while having the normal effect on the goal-tracking response. When analyzed with respect to whether participants were sign or goal trackers, the pattern changed. In sign trackers, the normal effect of context was observed on the keyboard responding: The context change lessened the effect of pre-exposure. In these people, there was no effect of context or pre-exposure on the goal-tracking response, though it was acquired. In the people

who were predominately goal trackers, the change of context further retarded the acquisition of key pressing but lessened the effect of pre-exposure on the goal-tracking response.

Those patterns, with respect to the characteristics attributed to sign- and goal-tracking individuals, provide clues as what was being learned in each group. Both sign- and goal-tracking rats are sensitive to strong devaluations of the outcome, and both seem to rely on error-correcting mechanisms (Derman et al., 2018). Nevertheless, goal tracking is described as resulting more so from topdown processes, while sign tracking is assumed to be driven in a more bottom-up manner (e.g., Flagel & Robinson, 2017). Much of that distinction comes from observing that the two behaviors depend on different neural circuitry. For example, sign-tracking rats exhibit a correlation in stimulus-induced c-fos mRNA activity between subcortical areas such as the nucleus accumbens shell and the paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus (PVNT), whereas goal trackers show correlation in activity between the prefrontal cortex and the PVNT (Haight & Flagel, 2014).

These bottom-up/top-down distinctions in processing between sign and goal trackers have carried over into describing humans (Colaizzi et al., 2020; Garofalo & di Pellegrino, 2015). Consistent with those characterizations, sign trackers are also more impulsive than goal trackers in both humans (Garofalo & di Pellegrino, 2015) and animals (e.g., Lovic et al., 2011). In rats, impulsivity, or rather its control in goal trackers, has been linked to executive functioning, particularly the ability to inhibit responding in operant discriminative responding (Enkel et al., 2019).

During pre-exposure, there was a weak tendency to respond on the keyboard that declined over exposure. That decline could result from a decline in attention to the sensor, as was evidenced in the eye-tracking data for both sign and goal trackers. Responding on the keyboard sometime during the game should be expected by the participants as such an expectation was set up in the instructions and practice trials. As suggested by McLaren et al. (2021), when stimuli are presented in a situation where making responses could be expected, pre-exposure might engage a response inhibition mechanism. Goal trackers, who are better able at inhibiting responding, may be learning to actively inhibit the response in the presence of the light better than sign trackers.

During conditioning, in the same context as where pre-exposure occurred, conditioning could be retarded by the decreased attention to the sensor in both of the pre-exposed conditions. In the different context, both sign and goal trackers may experience an increase in salience to the sensor, which would restore its associability. Such an increase may occur because the light is no longer primed by the context (McLaren &

Mackintosh, 2000; Wagner, 1981) or simply because of some arousal produced by its novelty in that context. In the sign trackers, that increase would manifest itself as better conditioning in the different context than in the same context as pre-exposure. In the goal trackers, however, the restoration of salience to the sensor could increase the expression of the response inhibition that these individuals have learned to the sensor in pre-exposure (see Kaye & Mackintosh, 1990, for a similar effect where a context change increases conditioned suppression performance), leading to less evidence of conditioning with respect to the keyboard. As no particular oculomotor response is necessarily expected or required by the instructions, there may be no basis for which inhibition of looking in any particular area of the screen should occur; thus, the goal-tracking response would not be affected by such inhibition and be better acquired in a different context.

That explanation leads to the question as to why the overall effect of context, without breaking the data down by sign and goal trackers, showed a more profound effect of pre-exposure in the different context than the same, when our prior experiment (Nelson et al., 2021) showed the opposite effect. One simple explanation may be that this experiment contained more goal trackers than did the previous one. It is not the goal tracking per se that produces the result, but rather the processes thought to be involved in goal tracking. Goal tracking suggests that the participants here were more engaged with the task with top-down executive processes leading to response inhibition as described in the preceding paragraph. The use of the eye tracker may have produced demand characteristics encouraging those top-down/executive processes. It has long been known that motivation to achieve is positively related to individuals' problem-solving ability (e.g., French & Thomas, 1958). In Nelson et al. (2021), participants were run in small groups (up to five) and were semi-isolated from each other and not monitored directly by any attending researcher. In the present experiment, participants were run individually, monitored by an eye tracker, and monitored by an attending researcher sitting roughly 1 m to their right. The eye tracking and the nearby presence of the attending researcher could produce stronger demand characteristics in the form of motivation to perform well on the task, which should encourage top-down and executive processes leading to response inhibition and also more goal trackers.

The results presented here with humans show that pre-exposure reduces overt visual attention to stimuli, and a context change does not necessarily restore that attention. When the stimulus is conditioned, and the outcome is localizable in space, gaze comes to be directed toward the location where the outcome is expected to occur (see also Nelson et al., 2019). An

increase in attention to the areas of the context where the outcome is expected will take attention away from the areas of the context where the outcome does not occur and may contribute to a lowering of overt attention to the predictive stimulus. A change in context between pre-exposure and conditioning had no effect on the orienting observed to the pre-exposed stimulus but did restore its ability to signal the forthcoming outcome as evidenced by goal tracking. In terms of the overt key-press response with instrumental/voluntary components, the change of context slightly increased the retarding effects of pre-exposure in participants overall. But when broken down by whether or not participants were sign or goal trackers, that effect was evident in the goal trackers, but the normal effect of less-retarded performance was evident in the sign trackers. These results, in comparison with previous ones using the same method, suggest that pre-exposure can engage both attentional and inhibitory processes. Demand characteristics produced by eye tracking may differentially affect the engagement of executive, top-down inhibitory processes and, as a result, may also affect the extent to which individuals sign and goal track.

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